

A NEW NEURO-FUZZY SYSTEM FOR TECHNICAL DEPENDABILITY ASSESSMENT

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Abstract

Purpose – the research builds a neuro-fuzzy system for technical system dependability assessment.

Methodology/approach – the problem data are obtained by observing the production process. The optimisation problem in operational safety is defined, specifying the input and output variables and the transfer function. We propose a fuzzy model with a neural network to identify the internal rules of the fuzzy system.

Findings – a new concept of dependability analysis of technical systems was formulated. It is subjected to quantitative analysis by implementing a fuzzy hybridised model with a neural classification technique.

Research limitations/implications – the limitation of the research consists in the fact that the generated neuro-fuzzy system is specialised for the technical phenomenon studied. Still, the impact of the research derived from the proposed methodology can be successfully applied in any quantitative analysis from any technical field.

Practical implications – practical importance through the methodology that uses hybrid techniques based on artificial intelligence and fuzzy logic for modelling the dependability function of any technical system.

Originality/value – a new problem in maintenance management with a new transferring function for the discrete optimisation problem. The research builds a new neuro-fuzzy system for modelling a technical system.

Key words: *Neuro-fuzzy system, Maintenance Management, Dependability assessment*

Introduction

The problem of maintenance management is taken from the textile industry in which four parameters are measured - two of production flow (*Production* and *Quality*) and two of maintenance (*Reliability* - through the *MTBF* parameter and *Maintainability* through the *MTTR* parameter). The data collected are from direct observation of the production flow in three textile units containing 28 rolling mills. The observation time is one month, during which the number of defects, the repair time, the production and the quality settings on the machines were observed.

The proposed modelling function is $P=f(M,R,Q)$, so we want to create a model with three inputs and one output. From previous research, the proportional dependence of the production parameter on the reliability parameter is known, and the easy correlation of the production parameter on the maintenance parameter. In the current research, we want to verify these two hypotheses and observe the effect of the quality parameter on the production parameter.

The problem is also present in other research works, being approached independently from the perspective of fuzzy systems (Vilcu et al., 2019), neural modelling (Vilcu et al., 2018), and mathematical modelling (Vilcu et al., 2016), with different modelling functions. The neuro-fuzzy approach is innovative in the area of analysis of the operational management of maintenance.

Neuro-fuzzy systems are viewed as neural networks with supervised learning that use multilayer feed-forward training algorithms. In neuro-fuzzy systems, the loadings of connections between layers and propagation and activation functions differ from classical neural networks (Mahmoud et al., 2015).

A neuro-fuzzy system generally has the following characteristics (Siminski, 2022):

- A neuro-fuzzy system is based on a fuzzy system in which the system of rules is generated by the neural network containing a learning algorithm imported from the theory of neural networks.
- A neuro-fuzzy system can be viewed as a neural network with supervised learning and feed-forward training algorithm with a three-layer structure. The first layer is characterised by the input variables, the inner (hidden) layer represents the fuzzy rules, and the output layer represents the output variables. The fuzzy sets are encoded as loads on the internal connections of the neuro-fuzzy system (figure 1)

Fig.1. Neuro-fuzzy system with a three layers internal structure

- Combines the positive characteristics of the two types of modelling - Neural networks - they are suitable for pattern recognition (classification) and less good in decision logic and fuzzy systems - they are effective in making decisions. Still, they have a disadvantage in making decision-making rules and especially in the moments when these rules are generated.
- Includes a classic fuzzy system: a fuzzy system is a set of rules (conditional statements) that transform inputs into outputs. A conditional statement is of the form: if x takes the value A , then y takes the value B . $\{x,y\}$ is called linguistic variables, $\{A,B\}$ are called linguistic values in the sets $\{X, Y\}$. Linguistic variable = variable whose values are words or sentences. Linguistic value = value or term that describes a linguistic variable (Al-Mahasneh, 2016).

The neuro-fuzzy system applied in this research combines these two analysis techniques, resulting in a neuro-fuzzy system (NFS). The mechanism underlying such a system is called neuro-fuzzy hybrid system (NFHS) - a neural mechanism that uses training and learning algorithms based on neural networks to determine the parameters of fuzzy systems.

The comparison of the two types of modelling with highlighting the positive elements is presented in table 1.

Table 1. Comparative modelling characteristics (Zheng et al., 2021)

Neural modelling	Fuzzy modelling
It does not require a mathematical transfer function	It does not require a mathematical transfer function
The learning system is permanent	Information about the system and its evolution must be known
There are learning algorithms	The learning system does not exist
It is a black-box type system	Simple implementation

A neuro-fuzzy system has the following architecture (figure 2).

Fig.2 Functional organisation chart of a neuro-fuzzy system

The functional organisational chart of a neuro-fuzzy system is presented in figure 2. It should be emphasised that the neural network works independently of the actual fuzzy system, and the structure of the fuzzy system is automatically generated by the neural network through a supervised learning algorithm (Ruspini et al., 2019).

The fuzzy rules are determined from the training data so that the neural network works independently of the fuzzy system, and the results of the neural network are used to initialise the fuzzy system. Clustering algorithms can be used to obtain fuzzy rules. Thus, the neural network functions as a rule base.

Organisation of research

The work is naturally structured by achieving the following objectives:

1. Choosing the technical phenomenon for the operational analysis of maintenance management. The data were collected by direct observation of 28 rolling mills from 3 textile units, during a month in which the number of stops and repair times were counted, and production and product quality were measured.
2. Formulation of the transfer function of the model proposed for analysis:

$$P = f(R, M, Q)$$

Where:

- R is defined by the parameter $MTBF = \frac{\sum \text{times of good operation}}{\text{number of defects}}$
- M is defined by the parameter $MTTR = \frac{\sum \text{stop times}}{\text{number of stops}}$
- Q is the quality that is given by the specifications on the technological flow
- P is the production value measured at the output of the technical devices

3. Formulation of working hypotheses:

H0: the production parameter is directly proportional to the reliability parameter

H1: the production parameter is easily correlated with the maintainability parameter

H2: the quality parameter has a slight moderating effect in models $P = f2(R, Q)$ and $P = f3(M, Q)$.

4. Formation of the neuro-fuzzy system using the Matlab2016a modelling environment, with the data obtained from the technical system organised in 2 groups - one for training (table 2) and another for verification (table 3).

Table 2. Neuro-fuzzy system training data set

MTBF (s)	MTTR (s)	Uster non-uniformity (%)	Production (kg/month)
72133	37004	2,432	8400
74800	40400	2,231	9792
270920	74680	2,122	13908
327718	87002	1,876	15675
119866	39641	2,512	8514
106426	31814	2,478	8820
10472	127768	1,993	1080
280833	64767	1,231	11570
57082	50438	2,498	5431
40771	39869	2,519	4671
50146	106945	2,591	3987
44847	70353	2,449	5144
42466	57487	2,472	5872
40385	54016	2,447	5784
22132	73868	1,721	4215
23915	109008	1,801	3424
38394	59526	1,829	3160
49244	73156	1,649	4445
67257	43143	1,761	8210
62216	48184	1,823	6624
68146	52290	1,699	7308
105177	60423	1,707	11175
118600	77241	1,791	10878

Table 3. Neuro-fuzzy system checking data set

MTBF (s)	MTTR (s)	Uster non-uniformity (%)	Production (kg/month)
111108	66929	1,722	10556
174365	74035	1,459	13488
162790	85610	1,498	13350
450726	46074	1,365	19152
159823	29434	1,521	11531

5. The results obtained by neuro-fuzzy modeling are analysed from the point of view of the researched hypotheses.

Experimental results

The applied procedure is:

1. In Matlab 2016a programming environment: Neuro-Fuzzy Designer application (control panel (figure 3)).

Fig.3 Neuro-fuzzy application control panel

2. Creation of data sets - training (train) and checking (check)

File New script -> copy data from excel (attention: decimal point)

The last series represents the values of the output variable, the first series – the values of the input variables.

3. Load the series in the application (File->Training and File->Checking)
4. The network is generated (Generate FIS) (figure 4)

Fig. 4 Neuro-fuzzy system

5. The neural network (NN) is trained by choosing the optimal training method (back-propagation algorithm or hybrid training algorithm) (figure 5).

Fig. 5 NN output data compared to training data

6. Checking the network on the test set (figure 6).

Fig. 6 Verification of the system generated by the NN

7. Load the previously developed model (figure 7) into the fuzzy application from the Matlab environment.

Fig. 7 Fuzzy system with structure generated by NN

The *MTBF* input variable with its membership functions is highlighted in figure 8.

Fig. 8 Membership functions of the Reliability input variable

The *MTTR* input variable with its membership functions is highlighted in figure 9.

Fig. 9 The membership functions of the input variable Maintainability

The Quality input variable with its membership functions is highlighted in figure 10.

Fig. 10 Membership functions of the Quality input variable

The set of rules automatically generated by the neural network is presented in figure 11 (graphical) and figure 12 (linguistic).

Fig.11 The set of rules given by the membership functions

Fig. 12 The set of linguistic rules characterising the internal structure of the fuzzy system

The model automatically proposes a set of 27 rules generated by the algorithm mechanism included in the neural network that initialises the fuzzy system.

Neuro-fuzzy model analysis of the two hypotheses

For modeling $P=f_1(R,M)$ (figure 13)

Fig. 13 Model $P=f_1(R,M)$

Explanation of the modelling function - Input1 represents the reliability function of the systems. We notice that with the increase of its value up to a certain threshold of $1,8 \times 10^5$, the value of the product increases proportionally. After this threshold, the production value decreases. The production parameter is proportional to the maintainability parameter over the entire range of values of this input, but the proportionality coefficient is minimal – a large increase in the maintainability parameter corresponds to a slight increase in the output parameter P . The neuro-fuzzy model validates the assumptions.

Determining the effect of the *Quality* variable on *Production*

Model $P=f_2(R, Q)$ (figure14)

Fig. 14. Model $P=f_2(F, Q)$

In modelling $P=f_2(F, Q)$ it can be seen that the quality parameter (input 3) does not have a determining effect on the production parameter. Thus, the quality parameter can be seen as a moderating parameter of the impact of the reliability parameter on the production parameter (P).

For modeling $P=f_3(M, Q)$ (figure 15).

Fig. 15 Model $P=f_3(M, Q)$

The model $P=f_3(M, Q)$ highlights the moderator character of the quality variable (input 3) which influences in a reduced way the effect produced by the maintainability parameter on the output parameter P (output 1). It is observed that there is a threshold value of the maintainability parameter (7.9×10^4) before which the evolution of the production parameter reaches a minimum value.

Discussion and conclusions

The neuro-fuzzy model confirmed the two analysis hypotheses of this research: the *Production* parameter of a maintenance management system is directly proportional to the *Reliability parameter* of the system being analysed; the *Production* parameter is easily correlated with the *Maintainability* parameter.

A second analysis of this research proved the moderating character of the *Quality* parameter on the two models $P=f_2(F, Q)$ and $P=f_3(M, Q)$ without radically influencing the values of the output parameter (P).

As future research wishes, it is the implementation of a neuro-fuzzy system with two outputs parameters for analysis with more complex modelling of the maintenance management phenomenon.

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